

Integration of Trove (Database as a Service) into the CERN OpenStack Cloud, and Evaluation of its Features

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ABSTRACT

This report details the integration of the Trove component of OpenStack, which provides Database as a Service, into the CERN cloud. It documents the steps necessary to get Trove working fully, including the process of creating datastore images for Trove to launch virtual machines with. It also compares Trove to CERN's own database service, Database on Demand.

Trove was also investigated in a 2014 summer student project, which can be found here: http://openlab.cern/publications/technical_documents/openstack-trove-evaluation-and-interfacing-cern-database-demand

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1. INTRODUCTION TO TROVE

Trove is the component of OpenStack that brings support for Database as a Service. In the simplest possible terms, Trove handles the creation of virtual machine instances using images that are preconfigured to be database servers, and provides an interface for managing the databases after their creation. Trove talks to the instances via RabbitMQ using a common set of commands, which are translated into database server specific commands by the Trove guestagent running on the instance. With this, Trove provides support for backing up databases, replicating databases, managing client user credentials for access to databases and more. Currently, Trove does not handle non-MySQL databases very well, as the instance overview and management sections in the Horizon dashboard for Trove do not change to reflect the features of the particular database being managed, and are always the standard MySQL management options.

The preconfigured images are registered with Trove as versions of a particular datastore, where the datastore is MySQL, MongoDB, etc. Each version of a datastore points to a particular image. The “version” does not specifically refer to the database server version, for example the MySQL datastore could have a version for MySQL server 5.6 on an Ubuntu image, and a different datastore version could be MySQL 5.6 on a Fedora image. When using the name “datastore” or “datastore version” I will generally be referring to the image itself.

2. MOTIVATION FOR TROVE

Trove could be used either as a replacement for, integrated with, or alongside CERN's current database service, Database on Demand (DBoD). Database on Demand was designed and is maintained by the IT-DB team at CERN, and is therefore well suited to the needs of its users. However, having Database as a Service available using Trove would consolidate the provisioning process for databases with the other resources available in the OpenStack cloud, and provide a more centralised experience for the end user. Trove is also a faster way to get access to a database, as there is an approval process for requests made to DBoD that users must wait for. This means that Trove can be more useful for creating a database, testing something with it, and then destroying it and creating a new one to test something else with. Or, quickly creating a database could be useful in a multi-staged workflow, where setting up a database is just one part of a continuous process. For instance, when introducing new physical hypervisors into the CERN cloud, the machines are split into groups of around 200 called cells. If the machines were not grouped like this, the bottleneck in the system would be in the single database that all the machines connect to. By grouping a limited number of machines into a single cell that uses its own database, the load on each cell's database is never enough to bottleneck the performance of the cloud. Setting up a new cell can take up to an entire day, and to be able to create a new database for the cell quickly would streamline part of this task.

The cost for this decreased waiting time is that the user then has more responsibility for the database after it has started running, rather than it being mostly the responsibility of the DBoD team to keep it running. In many cases, it may be worth it to wait for a database from DBoD for the performance and reliability required in a production database. On the other extreme, there is no reason why someone who immediately requires a database could not currently launch a standard virtual machine and manually install and configure a database server on it, but this is a tedious and repetitive task when many databases are required. Additionally, the user is then tied in to manually configuring the database and manually backing up the database, as well as storing and organising the backups.

Trove could possibly be used as a base to build a frontend for Database on Demand using the familiar OpenStack interface. With DBoD as a backend no functionality would be lost, but it would be possible to allocate resources and track the usage of them alongside the other cloud resources managed by OpenStack. This would be beneficial in the accounting process for assigning resources to the different experiments at CERN.

3. DEVSTACK

For any OpenStack component, using Devstack¹ is an easy way to get it up and running in a testing environment. This is how I first got Trove set up, and it helped to have a working example when trying to integrate the service into the CERN cloud. I wrote down step by step instructions for getting everything configured properly with Devstack, and they can be found online here², although a large part of it is now outdated as it relied on using prebuilt guest images which were available at <https://tarballs.openstack.org/trove/images/> that have since been removed.

4. CREATING A DATASTORE IMAGE

Using the prebuilt images was very useful to start with, as I could focus on getting Trove itself properly set up. Even so, the images needed quite a lot of modification to get fully working, and this involved mounting the image and editing the contents. The disk image builder³ tool provided by OpenStack is also fairly tricky to get working for Trove, but once you have it set up correctly only a few modifications are necessary to start producing images for different database servers.

First, an explanation of how the disk image builder (DIB) works. A number of “elements” are combined to form the final image. The base element is for the OS distribution you want to build on. Ubuntu and Fedora are the only two supported by the Trove specific elements, but the DIB can also build images for CentOS, Debian and even Gentoo. The base elements contain scripts that download the cloud images for those distributions and set them up ready to be modified by the elements that follow. Those elements then run their own scripts to install software or configure the image as necessary. The disk image builder has a large number of generic elements to use⁴, and Trove provides additional elements for adding database servers to the image⁵.

The disk image builder tool should not be run as the root user. Create a user account to build the images with.

```
$ useradd -m imagebuilder
$ sudo su - imagebuilder
$ sudo yum install python-pip
$ sudo pip install --upgrade pip
$ sudo pip install virtualenv
$ sudo pip install virtualenvwrapper
$ source /usr/bin/virtualenvwrapper.sh
$ mkdir venvs
$ export WORKON_HOME=~/.venvs/
$ mkvirtualenv dib
$ pip install diskimage-builder
```

The base elements required to build generic cloud images are included in the files installed with diskimage-builder. For Trove, the elements are available in two places. In the repository `openstack/trove-integration` and in the folder “integration” in the repository `openstack/trove`. DO NOT use `trove-integration`, as it is no longer updated.

```
$ git clone -b stable/ocata https://github.com/openstack/trove.git
```

¹ <https://docs.openstack.org/devstack/latest/>

² <https://github.com/trove-cern/devstack-setup>

³ <https://github.com/openstack/diskimage-builder/>

⁴ https://github.com/openstack/diskimage-builder/tree/master/diskimage_builder/elements

⁵ <https://github.com/openstack/trove/tree/master/integration/scripts/files/elements>

Aside from the list of elements which will be given in the build command, DIB also requires a number of environment variables to be set.

```
$ mkdir images
$ cd images
$ nano env_vars.sh
```

```
env_vars.sh
export WORKON_HOME=~/.venvs
export DISTRO_NAME=ubuntu
export DIB_RELEASE=xenial
export RELEASE=xenial
export CONTROLLER_IP=th-trove9.cern.ch
export HOSTNAME=th-trove9.cern.ch
export HOST_USERNAME=imagebuilder
export ESCAPED_PATH_TROVE="\home/imagebuilder/trove"
export USER=imagebuilder
export DIB_CLOUD_INIT_DATASOURCES=ConfigDrive
export HOST_SCP_USERNAME=root
export ESCAPED_GUEST_LOGDIR="\var/log/trove"
export SSH_DIR=/home/imagebuilder/guest-ssh-keys/
export
ELEMENTS_PATH=/home/imagebuilder/trove/integration/scripts/files/elements:/home/imagebuilder/venvs/dib/lib/python2.7/site-packages/diskimage_builder/elements
export REDSTACK_SCRIPTS=/home/imagebuilder/trove/integration/scripts/
export TROVESTACK_SCRIPTS=/home/imagebuilder/trove/integration/scripts/
export GUEST_USERNAME=trove
```

In the repositories for DIB and the Trove elements, the README in each element folder lists the environment variables required for the element, but most of the ones above are for DIB itself or for the base elements. The `DISTRO_NAME` variable could also be set to “fedora”, in which case the `DIB_RELEASE` and `RELEASE` variables would be a number such as 25, for release 25 of Fedora. `CONTROLLER_IP` is the IP or hostname for your Trove machine. By default, the startup script for the trove-guest service is set to copy the Trove code and configuration files from the machine at `HOSTNAME` using `scp` with the keys copied into the machine from `SSH_DIR` and the username `HOST_SCP_USERNAME`. `ESCAPED_PATH_TROVE` is the directory it copies the Trove code from on the host machine. In this case I also had a user called `imagebuilder` on the Trove machine, and had the Trove code cloned in that user’s home directory, but the path could also be set to the Trove code in the python site-packages directory on the Trove machine, or from the `imagebuilder` machine, as long as the SSH keys are set up correctly. This is useful for making changes to the configuration after starting a machine, but is not a secure method of doing so, since anyone who creates a machine using that image can then SSH from the instance into the machine hosting the Trove code. The recommended method to use in production is to insert the Trove code when the image is built, using the element “install-static”. The configuration files are injected by Trove when the machines boot, so they should not be included in the static files. With `GUEST_USERNAME` a user account is created in the guest image, and in this case it is with the username/password `trove/trove`.

Remember to `$ source env_vars.sh` whenever you make changes to this file.

With the environment variables set, a `disk-image-builder` command should look something like:

```
$ disk-image-create -o ubuntu-mysql ubuntu dhcp-all-interfaces vm cloud-init-datasources ubuntu-xenial-guest ubuntu-xenial-mysql
```


The `-o ubuntu-mysql` flag gives the name of the output file. If you run the command again with the same output name, the old image file will be renamed with a timestamp. Running this script with the environment setup as shown should successfully produce a guest image, but if the image were to be uploaded to glance, and registered as a datastore for Trove now, there would be one thing preventing the guestagent from starting properly. To fix this, only one change is needed. In the script which defines the service for systemd, we need to add an environment variable near the top of the script. We'll change the run requirements as well to make sure that it doesn't run when the network service is started but before a network connection is established. Changes are marked in red.

```
trove/integration/scripts/files/trove-guest.systemd.conf

[Unit]
Description=Trove Guest
After=syslog.target
After=network.target
Wants=network-online.target
After=network-online.target

[Service]
Type=simple
User=GUEST_USERNAME
Group=GUEST_USERNAME

Environment="PBR_VERSION=3.1.1"
.....Continued.....
```

Leaving the rest of the script as is. With this set, generate an image and it should be ready to upload and register with Trove.

```
$ disk-image-create -o ubuntu-mysql ubuntu dhcp-all-interfaces vm cloud-init-
datasources ubuntu-xenial-guest ubuntu-xenial-mysql
```

Install `python-glanceclient` on the image builder machine, and for convenience download an OpenStack RC file from the `openstack-dev` cloud. Source this file to set up your environment variables for authenticating with the CERN cloud.

```
$ pip install python-glanceclient
$ source openstackrc
$ glance image-create --name ubuntu16-mysql5.6 --disk-format qcow2 --
container-format bare < /home/imagebuilder/images/ubuntu-mysql.qcow2
```

The next step requires `trove-manage` which is installed in the package `openstack-trove-common` from repository `cern-centos-7-openstack`. Therefore, it is easiest to do this on the Trove machine itself. Using the image ID given in the output of the glance upload:

```
$ export IMAGE_ID=.....
$ trove-manage datastore_update mysql ""
$ trove-manage datastore_version_update mysql 5.6 mysql $IMAGE_ID "" 1
$ trove-manage datastore_update mysql 5.6
$ trove-manage db_load_datastore_config_parameters mysql 5.6
/usr/lib/python2.7/site-packages/trove/templates/mysql/validation-rules.json
```

The first command, with `datastore_update` creates the datastore for us to use. The first argument is the datastore name, and the second is to set the default datastore version. We don't have any datastore versions yet, so we need to pass it an empty string. The next command registers the image as a version

of the datastore we just created. The first “mysql” in the command is the name of the datastore, the second is the manager we want to use for this datastore version. As I understand it, the name could be anything as long as we created a datastore with that name, but the manager has to be set to an actual database server name so that Trove knows how to handle the image. The empty string is passed in place of a list of extra packages to install on the image when it boots, and the final integer is to set the datastore as active or inactive. We then use `datastore_update` again to set the default version of the datastore to the version we just created. Finally, we load the configuration parameters for the datastore version.

Creating a datastore image for another database server is in theory as easy as changing the final element for one for a different database. However, you can expect to run into some issues that may require changing the source code for the element scripts. For instance, when creating an image for MongoDB I ran into a problem where it was trying to install the MongoDB server version 3.2.6 specifically, and that version was no longer available from `apt-get`. By removing the constraint on the specific version, the disk image builder stopped crashing on the install stage.

5. LAUNCHING A DATABASE

With the image uploaded to Glance and registered as a datastore with Trove, it can now be used to launch a database server. This can be done through the Trove command line interface, or through the Horizon dashboard, in the Database -> Instances page. Some easy mistakes to make are:

Currently all volume types are listed in the Horizon launch form, but you may only have access to standard volumes. If you choose a volume type you have no access to or no quota for, the launch process will fail at the point when it tries to create the volume. This could be fixed by checking before launching the virtual machine that the user can access the chosen volume type, and could be made more user friendly by limiting the list in Horizon to only the available volume types.

In the initialise databases tab, the initial admin user cannot be a reserved name (for MySQL: “root” and “os_admin”), but in OpenStack version Ocata there is a bug that causes the wrong error message to be displayed if you do try to use one of these names. I submitted a patch⁶ for this bug but it can not yet be merged, so this issue will still be present in the next release version “Pike”.

When using the dashboard to restore from a backup, you are shown exactly the same interface as when launching a database. You must choose to restore from backup and select a backup file in the advanced tab, or it will just create a machine with a blank database.

6. MIGRATING FROM DEVSTACK TO THE CERN CLOUD

When using Devstack, all the necessary components of OpenStack run in a single virtual machine. In production in the CERN cloud, each component runs on its own virtual machine, or with its subcomponents split across a dedicated group of virtual machines. The process of detaching Trove from Devstack and attaching it to the CERN cloud instead is conceptually simple, but realistically requires a lot of work. The required steps are:

- Create a new virtual machine outside Devstack and install Trove in it.
- Copy the configuration files from Devstack to the new machine.
- Change the database endpoint in Devstack Keystone to point to the API URL of Trove in the new machine.
- At this point, Devstack should function normally again, but using the new machine for Trove.

⁶ <https://review.openstack.org/#/c/489125/>

- Change the endpoints in the Trove machine for Keystone, Nova etc. to the endpoints in the CERN cloud, and update other configuration parameters.
- Create an endpoint in the CERN cloud to point back to the Trove machine.

However, rather than using the same machine for the entire process, setting up a hostgroup and module for Trove in Puppet and creating a new machine entirely makes much more sense in the long term. Puppet⁷ is a configuration management system, and is used in the CERN cloud for deploying virtual machines which are then configured by the Puppet agent according to a specific set of instructions contained in a “hostgroup”. In our case, the Puppet agent will install Trove, write configuration files using values set in the hostgroup, and finally start the Trove services. Almost all of this is already provided by the Trove Puppet module⁸. This means that the only steps necessary in the hostgroup are to set the configuration values we want to use in the data section of the repository, and to import the various classes defined in the Trove module in a script in the manifests section. The module will handle everything else for us. Detailed documentation for using Puppet in the CERN cloud is available here⁹.

My hostgroup and module are here¹⁰ and here¹¹. The dev branch is the one currently being used for the host group, and the qa branch for the module.

7. ISSUES IN THE CERN CLOUD

The CERN cloud is not able to support Trove out of the box, as some OpenStack components that Trove expects to be available in the cloud are not there. Primarily, Trove expects the cloud to be using Neutron networking instead of Nova networking, so that it can apply security groups to the instances it creates. CERN is in the process of migrating from Nova to Neutron, but this was not yet available in the cells used for the Trove test instances. Secondly, Trove expects there to be the Swift component for object storage accessible for it to store database backup files and exported logs on, but this component is not used by CERN as other types of storage have been sufficient until now.

a. NEUTRON

Trove is not looking to find Neutron specifically, it is only trying to apply security groups to the instances it creates. When it does this, the launch procedure fails as it cannot find the security group it thought it just created. Applying a security group during the create_instance function can be skipped by setting the configuration parameter trove_security_groups_support=false in trove-taskmanager.conf. This is not usually changed, so to have it configured by Puppet it must be added to the Trove module in taskmanager.pp.

```
trove_taskmanager_config {
  'DEFAULT/trove_security_groups_support': value => false;
}
```

b. SWIFT

The easiest thing to do was to just start using Swift, rather than try to hack in some workaround solution. Currently, we have Ceph/S3 set up as a restricted endpoint in Keystone, which is available for Trove to

⁷ <https://puppet.com/>

⁸ <https://github.com/openstack/puppet-trove/>

⁹ <http://configdocs.web.cern.ch/configdocs/>

¹⁰ https://gitlab.cern.ch/ai/it-puppet-hostgroup-cloud_database/

¹¹ <https://gitlab.cern.ch/ai/it-puppet-module-trove/>

use. This serves as a drop-in replacement for Swift, and is already a supported service meaning we did not have to set up Swift from scratch. Another possibility to enable storage for backups and logs is a modification to Trove itself. The code responsible for interacting with the Swift object stores is located at `trove/trove/common/strategies/storage/swift.py`. The path to this file and the class inside it that should be imported, `SwiftStorage`, are both configurable in the guest agent config files (`storage_namespace` and `storage_strategy`). This class is designed to be able to be replaced by another method of storing data (it inherits from two classes, `Strategy` and `Storage`, which define empty methods that must be overwritten by the strategy), so it is entirely possible to write a storage strategy that would backup databases to a different storage backend. One more method could be to backup using volume snapshots, for instance. A blueprint already exists for this¹², and some code was written for it but the proposal was eventually abandoned. This method would be similar to how DBoD handles its backups.

Additionally, the Puppet module for Trove defaulted to generating the guestagent config file using a template rather than the values passed to `trove_guestagent_config` in `guestagent.pp`. Because of this, the region variable used by the guestagent was always the default value “RegionOne”, as region was not included in the template. This caused the Swift endpoint lookup to always fail. By adding

```
trove::taskmanager::use_guestagent_template: false
```

to the data section of the hostgroup, the value `trove::os_region_name: 'cern'`

would be respected, and be included in the generated config file.

8. COMPARISON TO DATABASE ON DEMAND

a. DATABASE CONFIGURATION

Trove and DBoD offer equivalent capabilities for the user to customise the configuration of their databases. Considering MySQL only for now, DBoD allows the user to download the `my.cnf` file being used by the database and upload a modified version. Trove uses the idea of “configuration groups” which can be applied to multiple databases.

¹² <https://blueprints.launchpad.net/trove/+spec/snapshot-as-backup-strategy>

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openstack

Configuration Group Details: higher-connections

Values Instances Details

Add parameters to the configuration group. When all the parameters are added click 'Apply Changes' to persist changes.

Displaying 2 items

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Value	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	max_user_connections	1000	<input type="button" value="DELETE PARAMETER"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	max_connections	1000	<input type="button" value="DELETE PARAMETER"/>

Displaying 2 items

Each database can only have a single configuration group attached to it, so to uniquely configure 10 databases would require 10 configuration groups, which have to be uniquely and descriptively named so that the user can differentiate them. This could be an issue with a large number of databases. There are several other drawbacks to using configuration groups.

- Configuration groups can not be duplicated, so to take a group being used by two databases and change a single value for only one of the databases, the user must create a new group and manually change all the values to be the same as the old group.
- When changing a parameter in a configuration group for the first time, there is no way to see what the default value is so that the change can be made relative to that, for example when increasing the maximum number of connections.
- Configuration groups are only valid for the datastore version they are created for. A group created for MySQL 5.5 on an Ubuntu datastore can not be used for MySQL 5.5 on a Fedora datastore, or MySQL 5.6 on an Ubuntu datastore. This makes sense in the grand scheme of things, but creating a configuration group that only changes the number of maximum connections for each and every datastore version, for example, might be annoying. There is no way to create publicly visible configuration groups in Trove either, the user must create their own groups for each datastore version in each project they want to use Trove in.

When a configuration group is changed, the changes are applied to all databases using that group. Most configuration parameters can be changed without needing to reboot the instance, but there are some where a restart is necessary. In this case, the instance is marked as requiring a reboot and this is made clearly visible in the instances list, where the default option on the actions menu is changed to the reboot option.

b. BACKUP AND RESTORE

Frankly, backup and restore in Trove leaves a lot to be desired. It uses mysqldump to create the backup files, and allows for incremental backups if a parent backup is selected. The only method for restoring a database is to launch a new instance, which then uses the backup file to populate the database. Clearly this isn't ideal, as in most cases you would want to roll back a currently running database to a previous state. Having a new instance with the backup loaded is useless if there are many clients that only know the hostname or IP for the old server. The DNS system at CERN is not able to quickly change the subdomain name to point to a new IP address, and since we don't currently have Neutron there is no possibility to just quickly switch over a floating IP address. DBoD also offers point in time recovery, which use the database snapshots along with the binary logs to restore the database to any chosen time, which is impossible with the method Trove is using.

c. STORAGE SIZE

In DBoD, the amount of storage allocated to each database dynamically increases as the database grows larger. This ensures that a database will never be using more storage space than necessary, and that there is always space to store new data on. Trove makes users choose a volume size in the creation process, which may be before the user knows how much space the database will need when it is actually being used. Trove relies on OpenStack's ability to resize volumes, but this does require around 30 seconds of downtime for the databases, as the volume has to be detached during the resize operation. In OpenStack version Pike, volumes can be resized without being detached. When the upgrade to the new version is complete, the resizing process could be automated to resize databases when needed, similar to DBoD. Currently the safest option for the user is to initially overestimate the maximum amount of storage space the database will need, but this leads to inefficient use of storage space, especially if the database never actually grows to be that large.

d. PROVISIONING AND RESOURCE USAGE

As already mentioned, one of the more attractive reasons to consider Trove is how quickly a database can be obtained by a user. There is no approval process to wait for, only the networking stage of launching a virtual machine, which takes around 10 minutes in the CERN cloud. Part of the reason for the delay in getting a database from DBoD is that each database must be registered with the identity manager, which ensures that when a user account expires its owned resources are transferred to the user's supervisor or another user. This system is already set up for reassigning OpenStack resources, and should easily extend to managing Trove instances.

The current distribution of database managers used in DBoD is:

- MySQL: 378 databases
- PostgreSQL: 110 databases
- InfluxDB: 53 databases
- Oracle: 9 databases

Trove supports MySQL and PostgreSQL, which make up the majority of databases in DBoD, but InfluxDB is being used more and more, and Trove does not have a guestagent for it, nor are there any plans to create one.

Database on Demand does not enforce any limits on how many databases can be created by a single user. Therefore it is the approval process which would prevent me from requesting 1,000 databases all at once and potentially disrupting the normal operation of the service due to the sudden influx of requests. Trove is limited by the per project quotas for CPUs, RAM, total instances, total volume size and number of volumes. It also implements a quota system internally which has a hard limit for the number of instances, volumes and backups that can be created per project, but this is not very well documented. The quota for the active project can be checked with the Trove CLI, using the command:

```
$ trove limit-list
+-----+
| Property      | Value  |
+-----+
| max_backups   | 50     |
| max_instances | 10     |
| max_volumes   | 40     |
| verb          | ABSOLUTE |
+-----+
```

There is no option to modify the quota limits, either through the CLI or in the Horizon dashboard, but the default values can be set in the configuration files, and are therefore also able to be set by Puppet. Setting these to very high values by default and letting the general project quota keep things under control might be preferable to having users being restricted by quota limits they can't even see without specifically searching for them.

As each Trove database server runs on its own virtual machine, there is a minimum cost in terms of resources for starting up a database, whereas DBoD runs multiple database servers on each machine. Currently for DBoD there are 15 virtual machines using 8 CPU / 16GB RAM that run 6 or 7 database servers each, and 15 virtual machines using 16 CPU / 30GB RAM that run 10 database servers each. This works out to about 1.5 CPUs per database server, and about 2.8GB of RAM. This is more than is allocated for an m2.small flavour machine, but less than either m2.medium or m2.large. Medium and large also have 20 and 40GB root disks, which are far larger than needed. Perhaps limiting Trove to creating instances with the m2.small flavour only could reduce the amount of resources being used unnecessarily. DBoD also has a set of physical machines which host 30-40 database servers each, which Trove would not be able to replicate.

e. MONITORING

DBoD has monitoring included in its web interface, both for the host machine and for the database itself. Integrating something similar into the OpenStack dashboard would most likely be very difficult, but an alternative would be to have each instance run its own web server to host the monitoring interface. Adding a link somewhere in the Horizon interface to send the user to host address of the machine would be much simpler than trying to add the monitoring to Horizon itself. DBoD uses Elasticsearch¹³ for monitoring, so it could also be adapted for use with Trove. The monitoring data is stored in an InfluxDB database and the frontend uses Grafana for displaying the information to the user. Having each database instance running this setup could impact performance, especially on the smaller instance flavours where RAM might be a limiting factor. There could also be issues integrating with Keystone authentication to make sure that only the database owner could access the monitoring. Alternatively, the data could be stored and hosted off the instances, in a centralised web portal.

¹³ <https://www.elastic.co/>

9. MISTRAL

Mistral, another component of OpenStack, was tested as a scheduler for automatic backups, but this did not work well due to problems in the current Mistral version. Using Mistral, the user can define workflows or use ones which are publicly available in the cloud to automate multiple actions in a single workbook. The workflow can be executed manually or run on a schedule using the cron system built into Mistral. However, a bug with trust credentials caused scheduled cron jobs to fail due to an authorization error. This is fixed in the next major release “Pike” but will not be ready in time for me to test.

Workflows are built up of one or more tasks, which execute actions. Mistral automatically generates the list of available actions by inspection of the APIs of the OpenStack components it can find in the cloud. There are currently over 100 actions for Trove, which cover all available methods in the API. A workflow is defined in a YAQL script which is uploaded to the workflows list.

For instance, a script that backs up a single database takes the Trove instance ID as an input, and defines two tasks. The first to find the database instance and store its properties in a variable, and the second to backup that database using the database name from the variable obtained in the first step as part of the name to save the backup with.

```
version: '2.0'

trove_backup_single:
  type: direct

  description: Backup a single databases in this project

  input:
    - database_id

  tasks:
    get_instance:
      action: trove.instances_find
      input:
        id: <% $.database_id %>
      publish:
        instance: <% task(get_instance).result %>
      keep-result: false
      on-success:
        - backup_database

    backup_database:
      action: trove.backups_create
      input:
        name: <% $.instance.name + "-" + now().format("%Y-%m-%d-%H-%M") %>
        description: Automatic backup
        instance: <% $.instance.id %>
```

This creates a backup of the database, and gives the backup a name combining the instance name and the current timestamp. The `get_instance` task uses the `instances_find` action available for Trove, passing it a value “id” to search for, and publishes the result of this action as a variable “instance”. This variable is used in the next task which performs the backup. It uses a built in function from YAQL “now” to get the current time and format it as a string. When the workflow is executed, it should be given an input in the format `{“database_id”: “9a1b67b1-00ab-4e9c-9607-d8dcc9ccb97”}` which is the instance ID from Trove, not the instance ID from Nova.

A workflow to backup all the databases in the current project is almost as simple.

```

version: '2.0'

trove_backup_all:
  type: direct

  description: Backup all databases in this project

  tasks:
    get_all_databases:
      action: trove.instances_list
      publish:
        instances: <% task(get_all_databases).result %>
      keep-result: false
      on-success:
        - backup_databases

    backup_databases:
      with-items: instance in <% $.instances %>
      action: trove.backups_create
      input:
        name: <% $.instance.name + "-" + now().format("%Y-%m-%d-%H:%M") %>
        description: Automatic backup
        instance: <% $.instance.id %>

```

YAQL loops over the list of databases from `get_all_databases` using the `with-items` syntax. This could be extended to check for backups which are older than a given number of days and remove them at the same time. The number of days could also be configurable as an input with a default value of several days.

Aside from backups, this way of defining workflows allows for endless possibilities for automating Trove. For instance, certain databases could have tweaked configuration groups applied to them at peak times in the day, or a workflow could add a given set of client access credentials to a database, and then remove them again after a defined amount of time. The Mistral API itself is included in the list of actions, which could be used for multi-workflow operations where the first workflow would schedule the next one to run at a later time and so on, but this might needlessly overcomplicate things.

10. BENCHMARKS

When the virtual machines are created, a storage volume is attached to the instance for the database to store its data on. The user can choose the size of this volume, and select from a list of different available volume types. The two performance tiers are standard and `io1`¹⁴. Standard is throttled to 100 IOPS per volume, and `io1` is throttled to 500 IOPS per volume. Under heavy load, databases are reliant on reading and writing data to the disk as fast as possible, therefore the speed of the storage should affect both the throughput and to some extent the latency of requests that can be handled by the database.

¹⁴ List of all available types: standard, `io1`, `cp1`, `cpio1`, `wig-cp1`, `wig-cpio1`. `cp1` and `cpio1` are critical power versions of standard and `io1` which are backed up by diesel generators, and the final two volume types are created in the Wigner cloud.

To test this, I set up three virtual machines, each using the m2.large flavour size. On two of the machines I had a 4GB volume attached, one standard and one io1. They were created using a datastore image for Percona server 5.6 running on Ubuntu 16.04, as that was the first image that I successfully managed to create with the disk image builder. The third machine I set up manually, without using Trove. This machine did not have a volume attached to it, so that the root disk of the instance would be used by the database. This uses the local SSD of the hypervisor, which is not throttled and can theoretically do up to several thousands of IOPS. However, this storage is shared between every other virtual machine on the same hypervisor, so being able to utilise all of that performance is impossible.

Sysbench version 1.0.8 was used for stress testing the databases. The read/write, read only, and write only modes were used, with varying numbers of threads. The process was automated using a script that can be found here¹⁵. Each machine/thread combination was benchmarked for a set amount of time. In tests that ran overnight, this was at least 10 or 20 minutes depending on how many tests were going to be run, so that any fluctuations in performance were smoothed out, and so that the databases had time to warm up.

The read/write benchmarks are difficult to extract information from, because it is unclear how the read and write performances are combined. Only the write only and read only benchmarks will be presented here.

In this benchmark, each machine/threads combo was run for 20 minutes, using the write only mode of sysbench. The results are in line with what we would expect to see. Most importantly is that there is approximately a 1:5 ratio between the standard and io1 types, which matches the ratio between the throttled input/output rates. The SSD storage is slightly faster. One of the things we were looking for was if being forced to use volumes was a significant bottleneck on the performance of the database. From this

¹⁵ <https://github.com/trove-cern/db-benchmark>

result, it seems that for a database where performance is critical, using io1 should give close to the best performance possible for heavy write loads.

The read only benchmarks were unexpected, to say the least. The clear dependence on the throttled number of IOPS that were seen in the write only benchmarks completely disappeared.

With the help of the IT-DB team, the conclusion we came to was that the entire database was being cached in memory, therefore the read only throughput would not depend on the storage type at all. This does not explain the reason why root is so much lower than standard or io1, however. For these benchmarks, sysbench had prepared the databases with 10,000 rows of data. To try and reduce the effectiveness of the caching, both the amount of data was increased and the database memory buffer size was decreased. The original memory buffer size was 1GB, and the 10,000 rows of data only needed several tens of MB of space. The number of rows being used was increased to 10,000,000. Using the following SQL command, the amount of data being used was checked.

```
mysql> SELECT (data_length+index_length)/power(1024,2) tablesize_mb FROM
information_schema.tables WHERE table_schema='sbtst1' and
table_name='sbtst1';
```

```
+-----+
| tablesize_mb |
+-----+
|          2130 |
+-----+
```

The memory buffer size was decreased to 32MB using configuration groups for the machines managed by Trove, and manually for the root machine. In each case, it was checked via the command line that the database had successfully applied the change.


```
mysql> show variables like "%innodb_buffer_pool_size%";
```

Variable_name	Value
innodb_buffer_pool_size	33554432

The benchmarks were run again.

It was not clear whether this was a problem with the benchmarks themselves, a problem with the configuration of the machines other than cache size, or somehow the actual reality of the volume performance.

a. COMPARISON WITH DBOD

This comparison is limited in its usefulness, as the Database on Demand database used in the tests is running alongside other databases. On the virtual machine serving the database used for benchmarking DBoD, ostest01, there were 5 other database servers running, for a total of 3 MySQL databases and 3 PostgreSQL databases. On top of that, the database was running a different MySQL version and there was also a significant difference in how the database was configured in comparison to the Trove databases, which used mostly default values. The MySQL version used by DBoD, 5.7.15, has performance instrumentation enabled by default which decreases the performance of the database as a side effect. Despite that, the DBoD database still outperformed both volume types and the SSD machine used in the previous tests by a large margin, in the write only benchmarks.

Database benchmarks write_only
 runtime=600s | table_rows=10000000
 1502226505 | 2017-Aug-08 23:08:25

In the read only benchmarks, once again the performance did not at all correlate with the write only benchmarks.

Database benchmarks read_only
 runtime=600s | table_rows=10000000
 1502216904 | 2017-Aug-08 20:28:24

This benchmark is the same as the last benchmark in the previous subsection, only with DBoD included this time. The memory caches for the two volume databases and the root database are still the decreased sizes, but the DBoD database is using a cache size of 1GB, as I did not have access rights to change the configuration.

It was possible that I could spend a lot of time trying to figure this out, but I decided to move on as at this point I still had to get backup and restore working, and to look into scheduling for automated backups, which were both more important.

11. CONCLUSION

Trove works as intended, and with some effort made to provide the other components it requires, can be successfully integrated into the CERN OpenStack cloud. Trove certainly does not provide as much functionality for managing databases as Database on Demand does, but it covers a slightly different use case - allowing users to quickly and easily provision a database for non-critical or testing purposes without needing to manually configure it. The next step is to determine whether or not this use case is something that would be used enough to justify the cost of maintaining Trove as a component in the CERN cloud and providing user support for it.

Another possible use for Trove is to use it only as a frontend in the cloud, and to modify it to use Database on Demand as the database backend. This would require a lot of changes to be made to both projects initially, but would integrate the database launching process into the familiar OpenStack interface while keeping the features and reliability of Database on Demand. It would also mean that the used resources could be managed by OpenStack, simplifying how the different experiments are allocated resources and how their usage of them is tracked.

